

Identity as a significant concept in mobilising collective action in mathematics education and beyond: A response to Lisa Darragh

Laura Black, University of Manchester, laura.black@manchester.ac.uk

It is my pleasure to be invited to offer a response to Lisa Darragh's plenary on 'Innovative learning environments and the digital era: Finding space for mathematics identity'. In doing so, I will argue that the concept of identity is not only useful in understanding students' and teachers' relationships with and participation in mathematics. Identities, like critical knowledge, are also potentially powerful tools in mobilising collective action that can be transformative of practice.

The myth of free choice and individualism

At first glance, Lisa provides an account of mathematics teaching and learning in Aotearoa that appears quite idyllic. This is especially so given my experience of an education system that is heavily regulated by central government (e.g. through standardised testing, a national curriculum etc.) and increasingly run in the interests of private businesses through the joining of schools into academy trusts (run by private trustees from business/charities), a predisposition towards consultocracy (Gunter, Hall, & Mills, 2015) and the outsourcing of curricula, resources and professional development to commercial enterprises. Whilst Lisa's account resonates with some of this, she also describes a localised curriculum that is devolved to the school level offering schools, teachers, parents (and students?) agency over what is learnt with potential to serve the needs of the community. With colleagues at Manchester, I have been involved in projects inspired by the Funds of Knowledge (FOK) approach (Moll, Amanti, Neff, & Gonzalez, 1992) and its more recent adaptation Funds of Identity (FOI) (Esteban-Guitart & Moll, 2014). Both of these approaches involve teachers working with oppressed/minoritized groups to locate knowledge and identities in the home and community as a resource for developing curriculum projects in schools. The aim is to connect the school curriculum to the 'everyday' knowledge, practices and needs students experience in their communities. So in one sense Lisa's description of educational policy in New Zealand seems to align with the fundamental principles of a FOK approach and its overarching aim of developing curricula that challenge the privileging of elite forms of knowledge (and identification) in the academic curriculum.

Yet Lisa critiques educational policies in New Zealand as maintaining the fiction of 'free choice' in pursuit of a neo-liberal subject who is then held accountable for such choices. Indeed parental choice has been long identified as an 'essential circuit' of neoliberal policy

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in education (Ball, 1994), which assumes notions of self definition, self actualisation and thereby individual responsibility for the success and/or failure of the child. According to this kind of critique, the fiction lies in the myth that choice proffers agency when in reality it is restricted to the privileged few – e.g., in the mathematics classroom this may be those in the right position to accept or reject what Lisa refers to as ‘identity scripts’ associated with success.

The concept of identity here is pertinent since, as Holland et al. (1998) note, any moment of (or engagement in) social activity not only involves what one does ‘in practice’ but also a self-authoring¹ of the subject in ways that are culturally or socially recognised for and by others. Thus learners in the mathematics classroom are not only subjectively experiencing mathematical practices they are also self-authoring as mathematics learners - or not - as the case may be. Indeed, Lisa notes how this self-authoring is framed by power relations when she states that “following the script is not always equally available for all people, and divergences from the script may be differently recognised depending on the person also” (Darragh, 2021, p. 23, in this volume). So how or why do policies that aim to give greater voice to students/parents/teachers become, ‘in practice’, a learning environment that is potentially stratifying and exclusive?

In the aforementioned work on FOK, we have offered a critique (using Bourdieu) of so called ‘domesticated’ versions of the approach for their propensity to surface capital in students’ homes in the interests of serving the needs of the school or the educational field (Black et al., 2019; Williams, 2016). Clearly those who have access to such capital are more able to offer the kinds of resources that the school might want or the kinds of identity scripts that are ascribed value in the mathematics classroom. However, the fundamental concern here must be with the structure of the educational field and the way its social, political and economic function is refracted through pedagogic practices. Such a critique suggests a more radical agenda is necessary whereby critical pedagogies are employed to challenge even transform (rather than serve) education as a process of reproduction.

The commodification of learning

Lisa’s focus on the identity scripts produced through Innovative Learning Environments (ILE) and commercial Online Mathematical Instruction Programmes (OMIPs) links acutely to debates around privatisation in education and the economic commodification of learning and teaching which I refer to above. Initiatives such as the introduction of Mastery Mathematics in England, exemplify the complex fuzziness of the private/public distinction in relation to forms of curricula/pedagogy innovation. Notions of pedagogy, curricula and learners are constructed in the name of ‘public value’ whereby responsibility for reform is shifted away from the institution (education system) but towards complex relationships involving ‘local publics’² (Newman, 2013) and private actors. Such initiatives involve the

¹ Note there are fundamental differences between self-authoring and neo-liberal concepts of self-actualisation as outlined by Holland et al (1998).

² Newman (2013) refers to new localism – where central functions of the state are devolved, fragmenting a unitary public in the name of flexibility, responsiveness and goals.

Identity as a significant concept in mobilising collective action in mathematics education

production/consumption of particular methods and resources which are in part public (i.e., openly stated as for the public good with public funds attached) but are also mobilized through both public (e.g., national organisations like NCETM) and private interests (e.g., paid consultants, academy trusts etc.). This complexity then produces particular relations of power between various stakeholders, and between organisations which permeate at every level. Quite literally this involves the commodification of students' educational labour for profit by private providers, which adds another layer to previous economic analyses of education whereby student labour is commodified in the form of qualifications that have value to be exchanged in the world of labour relations (Williams 2012).

However, Newman (2013) proposes a reconceptualization of 'public value' to incorporate a concept of 'public action', which involve new forms of alliance between activists, academics and policy actors. This arguably means such initiatives can potentially provide space for diverse collective forms of social agency and empowerment - that can lend themselves to more radical or progressive appropriations than we might otherwise see ventriloquated through policy discourse³. For instance: (i) alliance between teachers, academics and professional organisations which can produce collective agency for change (e.g., primary assessment reform); (ii) alliance between teachers within/across schools enabling some increase in professional autonomy locally; (iii) pedagogic practices which offer 'voice' to the mathematical learner and diverse forms of learner identity. Arguably, these forms of alliance engender ideas of voice and activism which are to be distinguished from the neo-liberal notions of 'free choice' and 'individualism' which Lisa alludes to. Public action engenders ideas of collective agency rather than the pursuit of private or individual gain.

Harnessing contradictions

Nevertheless, it is not my intention to dichotomise concepts here such as private/public, individual/collective and capital gain/human need. In Black et al (2021) we discussed how ideas associated with private capital gain (individual) and public good, collective agency and human need can be understood as a dialectic relation of exchange value – use value, drawing on Marx's concept of the commodity relation. In line with others in CHAT (Blunden, 2009), we argue for a unit of analysis which preserves the living dynamic unity of exchange value - use value and which, recognises this relation as fundamentally one of contradictory moments. Recognising and harnessing such contradictory moments can be developmental which can bring about transformations in practice. In the description Lisa offers, I suggest we might see such contradictory moments when the needs of a school community (run by parents) come into conflict or tension with the overarching 'need' of the school system to grow 'cultural capital' (exchange value) for those privileged enough to access it. For example, Lisa points out how some OMIPs promote a hyper individualisation of the learner (presumably to foster performances/actions/knowings that are transferable to standardised

³ Newman (2013) points out that marginalised or politically less powerful publics are more likely to be mobilised through autonomous groups rather than via official consultation and participation in established government.

tests) that conflicts with the diverse needs and interests of a community of learners as a group rather than as a sum of individuals. This raises a question: at what point might this community collectively decide to challenge the system as it stands? In CHAT terms, this is where the harnessing of contradictions can be productive through the creation of a shared joint object that motivates a group towards collective action through the kinds of alliances Newman refers to above.

And so to identity...

With the above in mind, I argue that the concept of identity is not only useful for exploring students' relationships and participation in mathematics education, identity or identities are also potentially powerful in mobilising collective action. Think, for instance, of the identity work taken on by oppressed groups that is central to so many struggles for change (e.g., we recently analysed the case of the Mexican American Studies programme in Tucson, Arizona; Black et al., 2021). But this requires a concept of identity that not only emphasises individual repetitive acts that come to carry cultural significance (as identity scripts) - it also requires some concept of motive (collective-individual) 'to act' and a sense of reflection on how our subjective experiences make sense in terms of who we are and what we are becoming (Holland et al., 1998). Change occurs not only through stylised individual performances (improvisation) but also through collective action and I argue that is through latter that imagined alternative identity scripts can be realised.

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